

TILSHUNOSLIKNING AMALIY MASALALARI: ZAMONAVIY TILSHUNOSLIKNING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI, YECHIMLARI, TARAQQIYOTI VA ISTIQBOLLARI

mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy anjuman

MATERIALLARI

2025-yil 29-30-sentabr

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
SIRDARYO VILOYATI HOKIMLIGI
GULISTON DAVLAT UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI BALIKESIR UNIVERSITETI,
TURKIYA RESPUBLIKASI FIRAT UNIVERSITETI,
YANGLING KASB-HUNAR VA TEXNIKA KOLLEJI**

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Mas’ul muharrirlar:

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To‘plamga keltirilgan ma’ruza tezislarning mazmuni, undagi ma’lumotlar va me’yoriy hujjatlar hamda fikr-mulohazalar, takliflarning to‘g‘riligiga mualliflarning o‘zlari mas’uldirlar

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value of traditional pedagogy. By doing so, educators can design more effective and engaging environments that prepare learners for the communicative demands of the technology-driven world.

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PARALINGUISTIC ELEMENTS IN CHARACTER DESCRIPTION AS A TOOL FOR FORMING INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: The article analyzes paralinguistic elements found in character descriptions within works of fiction and their potential for developing intercultural competence in foreign language learners. Drawing on the novels “Brothers and Sisters” by Fyodor Abramov and “The Man of Property” by John Galsworthy, the study identifies culturally specific features of non-verbal elements such as gestures, facial expressions, postures, and intonation. It also proposes methods for integrating these elements into the educational process. The research shows that working with paralinguistics in literary texts helps students develop skills for culturally appropriate interpretation and expands their intercultural competence.

Keywords: paralinguistics, intercultural competence, literary text, foreign language teaching, Abramov, Galsworthy.

1. Introduction.

Contemporary research in the field of foreign language teaching methodology [Hall, E. T., 1973. 150-155] emphasizes that successful intercultural communication requires not only lexical and grammatical competence, but also non-verbal competence. Paralinguistic means-gestures, facial expressions, posture, and intonation-play a key role in conveying emotions, social roles, and cultural norms [McNeill, D., 2005. 765-766].

A literary text is a valuable source for studying these means, as authors detail the non-verbal behavior of characters within a cultural context. Within the framework of this paper, special attention is paid to the character descriptions by Abramov and

Galsworthy, in which paralinguistics not only supplements verbal communication but also serves as a marker of cultural identity.

The goal of this study is to identify paralinguistic elements in literary texts in Russian and English and to propose methodological approaches for their use in foreign language education to develop intercultural competence.

2. Literature Review

Research into paralinguistic means as a part of communication has deep interdisciplinary roots, combining linguistics, cultural studies, psycholinguistics, and pedagogy. The term paralinguistics in its modern sense was introduced in the mid-20th century [Trager, G.L.,1958.12-13.] and includes the analysis of non-verbal components of speech such as timbre, intonation, and pauses, as well as descriptions of gestures, facial expressions, and postures that accompany verbal statements.

The study of paralinguistic elements is linked to the concept of non-verbal communication proposed in the cultural-anthropological research of E. Hall. Hall identified the concepts of proxemics (spatial distance), kinesics (gestures and body movements), and chronemics (the perception of time in communication) as key to analyzing intercultural differences.

For literary discourse, paralinguistics performs several functions:

- Characterization (creating a character's image through non-verbal details);
- Pragmatic (regulating interpersonal relationships);
- Linguo-cultural (representing national communication norms).

Uzbekistani linguists are also involved in the study of paralinguistic elements. Based on a detailed study of paralinguistic means in Uzbek, Russian, and English cultures, D. A. Abduazizova developed a detailed classification and proposed a comparative-typological method of analysis, substantiating the need to teach nonverbal behavior for effective intercultural interaction [Abduazizova D. A., 2002. 96-108]. G.B. Nadjimova investigated how nonverbal behavior in English and Karakalpak cultures, with its unique kinetic signals, reflects national mentality and traditions. This research made it possible to identify unique cultural codes for the perception and expression of emotions [Nazhimova G.B., 2023. 249-253].

In foreign language teaching methodology, paralinguistics is considered a part of intercultural competence. Learning to interpret non-verbal signals helps students avoid cultural misunderstandings and improves authentic communication skills. In this context, a literary text is a convenient and rich material for analysis because it contains culturally-specific paralinguistic descriptions that can be integrated into the learning process[Golubović, K, 2015. 47–56].

Thus, the current state of academic research confirms that paralinguistics is an integral part of communication and a valuable tool for developing intercultural competence in foreign language education. However, in pedagogical practice, the analysis of paralinguistic elements in literary texts remains underdeveloped, which highlights the relevance of this study.

3. Materials and methods

The research material consisted of Fyodor Abramov's novel, *Brothers and Sisters* (1958), and the first novel of John Galsworthy's trilogy, *The Man of Property*

(1906). These books were chosen for their character portrayals that make extensive use of paralinguistic elements-gestures, facial expressions, posture, and specific intonation and pausing.

Contrastive analysis allowed for the comparison of paralinguistic descriptions in the Russian and English literary traditions, revealing similarities and differences in culturally determined non-verbal behavior patterns. Pragmatic analysis aimed to define the communicative functions of these elements and their roles in conveying emotions, social roles, and interpersonal relationships.

Special attention was given to developing teaching methods that could be integrated into the foreign language learning process. As part of this approach, tasks were proposed that involved comparing, role-playing, and translating paralinguistic elements with commentary.

The criteria for selecting examples for analysis were: the presence of descriptions of gestures, facial expressions, postures, or intonational characteristics; their inclusion in the character's description; and their significance for understanding the character's emotional state or social role within the context of the work.

4. Results

Paralinguistic Element	Russian Prose (Abramov)	English Prose (Galsworthy)	Cultural Interpretation
Silence	A sign of inner protest or deep distress	A means of avoiding conflict	In Russian culture, silence is emotionally charged, while in English culture, it is pragmatic
Shrug	Indifference or bewilderment	Skepticism, irony	Different emotional connotations
Smile	A sincere display of emotions	A formal social gesture	In the English context, it is more often neutral
Averted gaze	An unwillingness to continue the conversation	A polite softening of a refusal	The Russian version is emotional

5. Discussion

The identified differences show that the interpretation of paralinguistics is impossible without considering the cultural context. For foreign language teaching, this opens up broad methodological opportunities:

Comparative exercises: Students are given excerpts from Russian and English prose and compare gestures and facial expressions.

Role-playing: Acting out scenes and adapting non-verbal elements to different cultural codes.

Translation with commentary: Emphasis on conveying not only the words but also the non-verbal component.

Such tasks develop students' ability to notice and correctly interpret culturally marked non-verbal signals.

6. Conclusion

Paralinguistic elements in literary texts are an important tool for developing intercultural competence. Their analysis helps students not only better understand a literary text but also develop skills for effective intercultural communication. The inclusion of paralinguistic analysis in the educational process contributes to the formation of a holistic view of language as a complex system that unites verbal and non-verbal components.

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ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA MATN YARATISH

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola ona tili darslarida matn yaratish jarayonini takomillashtirishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar va innovatsion metodlarning ahamiyatini o‘rganadi. Tadqiqotda Mind mapping, Brainstorming, Drafting and revising kabi metodlar va Google Docs, Grammarly, Padlet kabi texnologik vositalardan foydalanishning yozma nutqni rivojlantirishdagi samaradorligi tahlil qilingan.

Mualliflar zamonaviy texnologiyalarni integratsiya qilish o‘quvchilarning mustaqil fikrlash, tahlil qilish va ijodiy ko‘nikmalarini sezilarli darajada oshirishini ta’kidlaydi. Maqola ona tili o‘qituvchilari uchun amaliy tavsiyalar berib, ta’lim sifatini yaxshilashda yangi pedagogik yondashuvlarni qo‘llash zarurligini ko‘rsatadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: pedagogik texnologiyalar, matn yaratish, innovatsion metodlar, yozma nutq, interaktiv ta’lim, fikrlash ko‘nikmalari

Annotatsion. This article examines the importance of modern pedagogical technologies and innovative methods in improving the process of text creation in native language classes. The study analyzes the effectiveness of using such methods as Mind mapping, Brainstorming, Drafting and revising, and technological tools such as Google Docs, Grammarly, Padlet in developing written speech. The authors emphasize that the integration of modern technologies significantly increases